

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.5 Social media analysis / IPBES transformative change assessment

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Description

The social media analysis is part of chapter 2, “Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people” of the IPBES transformative change assessment. The chapter encompasses a variety of sources, which contain visions of desirable futures in an environmental context, including a crowd sourced approach – social media data analytics. To collect such visions from social media, two different approaches were used. First, visions in social media-based peer-reviewed studies were searched via Web of Science and Scopus platforms. Second, X (formerly Twitter) data were analyzed as X is one of the world’s most popular microblogging platforms for sharing brief textual narratives.

Process Overview

Protocol

Step 1

Type of analysis/search/review: Academic literature search

Search languages: English

Search engine: Scopus, Web of Science

Exact date of the search: July 2022

Search terms and sample extracted:

- 3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.5_data_rawSOCMED_67.csv
- 4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.5_data_rawSOCMED_17.csv

Search terms	Sample extracted
"twitter" AND "vision*" AND ("biodiversity*" OR "nature*" OR "environment*")	67
"social media" AND "public view*" AND ("biodiversity*" OR "nature*" OR "environment*")	17

Location and format of the data: 5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.5_social_media(A).csv

Treatment applied: Initial searches in Web of Science and Scopus, using the following terms ("vision*" AND "social media" AND "future*" AND ("biodiversity*" OR "nature*" OR "environment*")) resulted in 102 scientific papers. However, after pre-screening of titles and abstracts, it proved ineffective, as ‘vision’ predominantly referred to computer vision techniques and no relevant papers were found. Therefore, the search terms were adapted as described above. After pre-screening titles and abstracts, two additional papers were selected for inclusion in the chapter.

This search was complemented using Google Scholar and other relevant queries. As a result three additional papers were selected and used.

Step 2

Type of analysis/search/review: Social network search

Search languages: English

Exact date of the search: 23 June 2022

Search engines: Twitter Academic API (Application Programming Interface)

Search terms: "vision biodiversity" OR "vision environment" OR "vision nature" OR "vision ecosystem" OR "future environment" OR "future biodiversity" OR "future nature"

Search period: 25 May 2022 – 25 May 2023

Sample extracted: 271,109 tweets

Treatment applied: Using the “academictwitterR” R package (Barrie & Ho, 2021), tweets were collected for a 1-year period with their respective metadata and anonymized authors. A topic modelling procedure was conducted, as implemented in the BERTopic algorithm (Grootendorst, 2022) and classified the 271,109 tweets into 444 topics. The topics were visually screened, topics and their associated tweets that were not relevant to the analysis were excluded, with an accuracy classification score of <0.5. The remaining 7,925 tweets

were additionally screened according to their relevance for the analysis of the visions, and 962 tweets containing positive visions for the future of nature and people were retained.

Location and format of the data: License restrictions do not allow researchers to share further once X/Twitter data is retrieved for academic analysis. A small sample for testing purposes is available via

GitHub: https://github.com/oleksandrkarasov/IPBES_TC_social_media

Code scripts and interactive charts are available via

GitHub: https://github.com/oleksandrkarasov/IPBES_TC_social_media

References

Barrie C, Ho JC. *academicwitterR*: an R package to access the Twitter Academic Research Product Track v2 API endpoint. 2021. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 6(62), 3272. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03272>.

Grootendorst M. BERTopic: Neural topic modelling with a class-based TF-IDF procedure. 2022. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.05794>.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
1	1-IPBES_TCA_chapter 2_DMR 2.5_social_media_analysis	pdf	353 Ko	Data management report
2	2-IPBES TCA_chapter 2_DMR 2.5_social_media-process	jpg	145 Ko	Figure description of the process
3	3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.5_data_rawSOCMED_67.csv	csv	13 Ko	67 hits
4	4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.5_data_rawSOCMED_17.csv	csv	4 Ko	17 hits
5	5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.5_social_media(A).csv	csv	2 Ko	8 references included in chapter 2 analysis